

Информационен резонанс на книгата “The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes” (A Hunger Games Novel) от Сюзан Колинс

Информационен мониторинг и библиометричен анализ
(2020-2023)

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Дата: 09.06.2023 г.

Увод

Обект на настоящото проучване е книгата “The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes” („Балада за пойни птици и змии“), написана от Сюзан Колинс. Мотивите за избор на обекта са високите очаквания от страна на читателите и издателите, противоречивите коментари, отзиви и критики за книгата, както и предстоящата премиера на нейната екранизация.

Целта на настоящото проучване е да се открият доказателства, че книгата „The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes“ на Сюзан Колинс се е осъществила като медия.

Задачите, посредством които ще се изпълни целта, са: първо, да се намерят и представят различните форми на информационен резонанс на книгата във всяка от осемте фази на алгоритъма за информационно търсене на информационен резонанс на книга; второ, получените резултати да бъдат обобщени и визуализирани чрез диаграми; трето, да бъде направена рекапитулация на резултатите чрез количествено обобщение и четвърто, да се

направи финален извод като се отговори на въпроса „Осъществила ли се е книгата „The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes“ като медия?“.

Методиката, която ще бъде използвана в настоящето проучване, включва информационно търсене, информационен мониторинг и библиометричен анализ. За извършването на библиометричен анализ ще бъде използван инструментът „Алгоритъм за информационно търсене на информационния резонанс на книга в 8 фази“, разработен от М. Цветкова.¹

Обхватът на проучване включва всички формати на книгата. За информационния мониторинг ще бъдат използвани всички български и чуждестранни канали, които могат да доставят данни за публичен информационен резонанс на книгата. При проучване на симултанни онлайн практики и пряка обратна връзка няма да има ограничения в езика и изданията на книгата. Информационният мониторинг ще обхване периода от 2020 до 2023 г.

Обект на информационен мониторинг

Метаданни на обекта (английски език):

Author: Suzanne Collins

Title: The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes

Publisher: Scholastic Press, New York, NY, 2020

Physical Description: 517 pages; 22 cm.

Edition/Format: Print book

Subjects: Contests and competitions; Survival skills; English teen; Science fiction

Genre/Form: Dystopian novel; Science fiction novel

Document Type: Book

All Authors / Contributors: Suzanne Collins

ISBN: 9781338635171, 1338635174

OCLC Number: 1161996489

¹ Tsvetkova, Milena. Reading as Communication Echo: Scientific Model of the Reader's Feedback Research. Saarbrücken, Germany: Lambert Academic Publishing, 2017. 120 p. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3204060>

Изобр. 1. Корица на английския оригинал на „The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes“ (2020 г.)

Метаданни на обекта (български език):

Автор: Сюзан Колинс

Издателство: Екслибрис

Година на издаване: 2020 г.

Издание: Мека корица

Брой страници: 496

Вид продукт: Романи

Жанрове: Антиутопии, Приключенски, Фентъзи

Тема: The Hunger Games (Игрите на глада)

Оригинално име: The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes (A Hunger Games Novel)

Език: Български

Националност: Американска

Преводач: Илиян Лолов, Неза Михайлова

ISBN: 9786197115420

Поредица: Игрите на глада

Размер на опаковката: 18 x 4 x 12.5 см

Изобр. 2. Корица на българското издание на „Балада за пойни птици и змии“ (2020 г.)

Информационно-резонансното (медийно-рефлексивното) поле на книгата „The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes“ - реакциите на читателите ѝ във вид на обратна връзка, ще бъде проследено чрез информационен мониторинг последователно по 8 основни фази:

- I. Симултанни онлайн практики и директна обратна връзка (с автора);
- II. Номинална (формална) обработка - библиографско описание, преиздание; едукция (аналитико-синтетична обработка) на съдържанието - класифициране, предметизиране (извеждане на ключови думи); анонси, анотации, резюме, реферат; съкратени версии на книгата;
- III. Репродукция (деривация) - цитиране, перифразиране, ремиксиране, фен творчество (фенфикшън), преводи;
- IV. Текуща (оперативна) критика - ревю (преглед); търговски и читателски класации;
- V. Експертна (научна) критика - професионални награди; изследвания и интерпретации;
- VI. Медиаморфози (медийни репрезентации, продължения, трансакции, транскодиране, трансмутации, конвертиране на книгата в друг медиен формат) - екранизиране на книгата, поставяне на сцена като театрална постановка и други практики, форми и изкуства, появили се в следствие на прочита на книгата;
- VII. Историзация (меморизация и митологизация).

Фаза 1. Симултанни онлайн практики и пряка обратна връзка

В тази фаза ще бъдат търсени коментари за книгата „The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes“ на Сюзан Колинс в социалните мрежи *Goodreads* и *Library Thing*. В *Goodreads* ще се търсят само коментари с текст без ограничение в езика. За коментарите в *Library Thing* няма ограничения в търсенето. Ще бъдат търсени коментари за книгата „The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes“ в онлайн книжарниците „Хеликон“ (*Helikon*), „Сиела“ (*Ciela*), „Озон“ (*ozone.bg*) и *Store.bg*. Периодът на търсене е 2020-2023 г.

1.1. Коментари в социални мрежи

Ще бъдат отразени коментарите в социалната мрежа *Goodreads* и *Library Thing*. Коментарите са разделени спрямо изданието, което е коментирано и в хронологичен ред.

Коментари в Goodreads:

The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes. In: Goodreads, 2020. Available from:

<https://www.goodreads.com/book/show/51901147-the-ballad-of-songbirds-and-snakes>

Най-стари:

“*whispers softly*: fuck

whispers louder: this book releases tomorrow and if I see any of you posting even the mildest spoilers in your status updates you'll have a safe place in hell that looks exactly like the 74th Hunger Games

yawns: 60% in and I can't make myself care so I'll just finish this some other time...or not " Kai Spellmeier's review. In: Goodreads, 8.10.2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2861333461> [07.06.2023]

“When it was first revealed that this will be President Snow’s prequel story, I have to admit that the anti-hype, which immediately arose around this, rubbed off on me as well. This resulted in me going into this with low expectations. But I need to clear something up. This *isn't* The Hunger Games. Nothing will ever be like

The Hunger Games, and this book definitely *isn't* trying to be like The Hunger Games.

This book is about Coriolanus Snow when he was just a student in a post-war Capitol. The world it takes place in feels completely different. *Is* completely different. The war has taken a toll on the districts, but on the Capitol more than anything else. No big money is being spend on a fashion trends or on the Games; hell, some people barely scrape enough for a living. The Games have been around for 10 years, indeed, but they're lacking their viewers. (Can you even imagine a situation like that? Gale's dream come true? "*No one watches, they don't have a game.*")

This is a *prequel* story. Of how The Hunger Games were born. And who'd better tell it than a man whose story is a part of it? Who was there at the beginning and there till the end? Someone we are familiar with, someone we know we hate, but we don't really know anything about him. About his past. This story is no justification for his future actions. If anything, it's explanation." Katherine Stargazing's review. In: Goodreads, 23.06.2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2861337534> [07.06.2023]

“I'm done!! It only took 68 days but I finally finished this f*cking book!!!

Although I did find parts of this book boring, ultimately it only took me so long to finish because I fell into the worst/most specific book slump I have ever been in. All I was in the mood to read was romance novels. Specifically, romances I can actually get behind, and not what was in this. I love a good romance subplot, but Snow and Lucy Gray just made me feel kinda ick, especially from Lucy Gray's side of things. It just felt exploitative (which if that was the point, wasn't made clear enough) but also unnecessary. A huge part of The Hunger Games was how Katniss weaponised her "romance" with Peeta and also had it turned against her. It was made into this construct that actually had a specific part in forwarding the plot, while in this I *think* it's meant to play a part in guiding Snow into becoming a person who prioritises ambition and control over everything else. It so easily could have been swapped out for some other guiding force that the romance is made redundant. And because it's been done so many times before in an antagonist's backstory: cheap and unoriginal. I will say, [Suzanne Collins](#) does do a fantastic job

of showing how Snow thinks and justifies his thoughts and actions, and it certainly did give me better insight into his character and motivations. I was successfully made to think from the point of view of the Capitol and Gamemakers, and started to imagine what I could do if I were in Snow’s place. It was interesting to see the Games so early on in their creation and compare it to how they are 60 years later for Katniss. But that’s about it. I personally don’t think that’s enough to warrant a 500+ page book.

That’s my main problem with this book, it didn’t add enough to make it an exciting, new addition to The Hunger Games series. The world, while different, is still quite similar to how it is in [The Hunger Games](#), and we only get to visit the same locations. The Capitol, the arena, and District 12. Snow himself, while intriguing, doesn’t transform enough into the man we know from the main series. I personally think this would have been better if it had been a novella or covered more of Snow’s life. I was hoping we were going to get to see his political scheming and read about how he climbed the ladder to become the President. We see a hint of that by the very end of the book, but for the most part Snow is just a character that got tossed around by the events of the book, rather than being the person to create, orchestrate or manipulate them. This even has a personal bookish pet peeve of mine where Snow does something "seemingly out of his control, as if his body has a mind of its own". Yes, it does, Snow’s mind. So tell me why he is doing what he's doing even if he's denying the reasons to himself.

I was one of the people that defended this book up until its release date, cause I was hoping that we'd all be proven wrong and that [Suzanne Collins](#) would have something up her sleeve that would make President Snow's story worth hearing. I still do believe that people were too quick to condemn a book before it had even been released and anyone had had a chance to read and review it, but I gotta say, I don't really see the point of this book. It's not bad by any means, but it certainly doesn't live up to its predecessors.

P.s. I am absolutely referring to Snow as 'Snow' because I can't remember his first name properly, and I refuse to refer to him as Coryo in my review.” Darcy (Daydreamingofbookdragons)'s review. In: Goodreads, 27.08.2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2861337657> [07.06.2023]

“It’s been a while since I’ve delved into a book, but Suzanne Collins brought me back in! I was very scared because the original series is so good and I know it could be hard to live up to those standards. Now, after finishing the book, I am excited to say that it did not disappoint. It is exactly what I wanted from a book about President Snow. I know people were concerned about the story “humanizing” President Snow but Suzanne does not paint him as a “good” guy from the get go. President Snow has his opinions about the districts and the Capitol and he doesn’t stray too far from them throughout the book. Every action he makes is for power and glory. There’s a point where he does wonder off his path (this is where I was very concerned about his character and the story overall) but by the end he becomes exactly the person he was meant to be. I usually do a Pro and Con list but I really enjoyed this book. The only Con I have is that it may be a little too long, but the end makes up for that. I felt the third act was the weakest, but I realized that it serves a purpose. The third act is so important because it is in this act where Snow realizes that he lost his way towards power and tries to fix it. The first half of the book (The lead up to the games and the games itself) was fresh, exciting, and gruesome. It’s definitely not the Games we know in Katniss’ lifetime. It was nice to get a look at the development of the games and how different it was from the start.” Isaac Reyes’s review. In: Goodreads, 17.08.2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3348142094> [07.06.2023]

“When the summary for this book was released, it was pretty contentious. A lot of people immediately rated it 1 star on GoodReads based solely upon the fact that the character we follow is President Snow. There was worry that the book would justify his actions, people wanted the story of Mags’ games or any number of other characters besides Snow himself. I had my doubts but I like Snow’s character in the books, I think he’s an excellent villain, and let’s be honest, I was going to read this book no matter who it was about.

This book takes place during the 10th anniversary of the Hunger Games. The memory of the war and rebellion is still fresh and the Games are fairly new to the citizens of the Capital and districts alike. Unlike the 74th HG that we witness in the first book, these games are not a spectacle or a reality show. It’s mostly just a

bunch of starving kids thrown into a gladiator style fighting arena with a pile of weapons to fight to the death. A lot of citizens are not tuning in to watch it because it's too gruesome and watching starving children fight and die is not entertainment to them. Dr Gaul, the head Game-maker is trying to increase viewers and thus trying new methods to make the Games more popular. They introduce a host, betting, sponsors, and mentors from the Academy in the Capital.

With the demise of district 13, the Snow family lost all of their assets and are desolate, living in poverty while living in a penthouse. They have no money and are just scraping by while doing their best to keep up appearances because they do not want people to know how far they've fallen. Coriolanus secures one of the coveted mentorships in the hopes that he can win and get a prize that will fund his education at the University, bringing the Snow family back to the top.

I really enjoyed this book. I thought the history of the games was a fresh way to have another book that features the games without it being redundant. We saw the 74 & 75 HG from the perspective of the tributes so having the games themselves be so different and also be from the perspective of a spectator and mentor still gave us the Games but in a new light. It was a change that I think was necessary in order to create a unique story that would stand out against the OG trilogy while also standing well on its own. The evolution of the games was also something that I love learning about. It makes sense that it didn't start out the way we see them in the trilogy and I liked watching them evolve. The Games were not always palatable to Capital citizens, they were conditioned to it through showmanship, sponsorship, betting, interviews, all the things that make the games the games that begin to develop in this book.

Music also played an integral role in this book. I never really considered the importance of music in the OG trilogy, but looking at this book and comparing it, it really is important to the story. The mockingjays that both symbolize the rebellion and are also something that survived despite all odds, Katniss' singing to Prim and to Rue, Katniss singing for Pollox and the mockingjays picking up her song... It's everywhere and that carried on in this book as well.

If you were worried that this book would show Snow as a likable guy, justify his choices, or redeem him in any way, don't. That's not what this book does. Snow

does make some of the right choices, but generally they are for selfish reasons. His only motivation is power and reclaiming his family's position on top. He tries to justify a lot of his actions, saying he had no choice or that it was necessary. He's not a good guy. But I kept wanting to learn more. It's a villain backstory so he definitely starts out as a normal kid but there's still some thoughts going on his mind that show he is playing chess instead of making choices for the right reasons. He's always selfish; even when he's helping others it's for his own benefit. And he becomes harsher and worse as the story moves on. I really liked this

The only negatives I have to add are that there is a lull in the pacing starting at the beginning of Part II. It's necessary and the action does build back up. I thought the ending was a little lackluster, I'd have change one specific moment. And the characters in this just are not as good as the first one, mostly because you don't empathize with them as much. The tributes and victors are easier to connect with in the original trilogy. The Capital kids are just not as likable.” Books With Kayla's review. In: Goodreads, 21.05.2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3000872203> [07.06.2023]

“Update 1: that cover is so ugly lmao i keep looking at it and its just... so ugly and generic

Well... I'm not sure how to rate this. Mostly bc im still not sure if Snow was the right person to use to give us more history of the world. I mean it makes sense since he's the overall villain of the series but it made this book a little tedious. How am i supposed to feel anything for this character when i KNOW who he's gonna end up being. His character was already extremely possessive and controlling. He had some pseudo sympathy for lucy but not any other tribute. and even his feelings for lucy seemed off since he kept referring to her as someone to use but told her she was important to him as a person?? and his affections were very possessive and territorial so i just kept thinking girl you better run while you still can So it makes sense that he'll end up as the tyrannic dictator that he was clearly always destined to be. But like... listening to 18 hours of his villain story? And for what? To find out why he hated mockingjays and District 12 so much? I'm honestly conflicted. Bc i like that we got this information but i would have liked someone else's backstory

first and then snow’s maybe. Idk i just really hate him and reading a book from the pov of the character you hate just seems annoying at times lol

Anyway, suzanne collins is still a great writer so i enjoyed the book but i still very much hate snow. Loved the side characters and the background and depth it added to the world. We get the origins of the “hanging tree” song as well (im lowkey still mad the narrator of the audiobook messed up and didn’t sing ANY of the songs. Like there’s literally already a melody of that song out in the world it would’ve been so EASY to just use it!!!)” Love, Celina’s review. In: Goodreads, 02.07.2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2861338428> [07.06.2023]

“I don’t know what to think about it. Lots of connections to The Hunger Games that I did enjoy. Really loved the songs! More thoughts later.” Noelle’s review. In: Goodreads, 03.06.2020 Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2861354286> [07.06.2023]

“ARE YOU KIDDING ME” Emma *insert corn here*’s review. In: Goodreads 03.02.2022. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2861355716> [07.06.2023]

“i’m ready for my queen suzanne to return” julianna ↗s review. In: Goodreads, 29.02.2022. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2861370479> [07.06.2023]

“*pterodactyl scream into the void*” Merline’s review. In: Goodreads, 16.02.2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2861369538> [07.06.2023]

“I definitely had mixed feelings towards this book and went into it with pretty low expectations, but by the last few chapters I ended up loving it!!! It’s important to note that this doesn’t redeem Snow in any way that I could see. The way the point of view was written in this book did confuse me because for a good portion of it I was honestly confused about how we were really supposed to feel

about Snow while he kept mentioning how poor his family is and how often he was presented as being neutral or didn't approve of things the Capitol was doing, but while he totally thinks he was the hero of this story, the reader will know that what he did was wrong. He's an ambitious, ruthless, awful human, and this book does a great job in (slowly and sometimes boringly) showing us the development of this, which is the whole point of this prequel.

Lots of people will probably either just avoid it or stop reading halfway through because the ending does drag on to where it gets pretty boring and this is a philosophically heavy book so I'd say calling it YA is a little iffy, but personally, the ending really made it for me. The first 75% I'd rate 3/5 stars, and the last part would be 4 or 4.5 stars, and I'm just going to round it up because it's The Hunger Games series and it has a special place in my heart.

I don't usually say this about long books, but this one felt like the first 75% was too long with *so many* boring parts that had a few intense moments throughout. The Games had their moments, but overall I didn't like the fact that we were stuck with Snow for it all with only brief updates of tributes dying. If I went back to reread it I know I would pick up more on small details that really made their impact in the final chapters which would probably help with keeping my interest, but overall I'd say if you're a fan of this series, push through the beginning and middle for that ending because it's so worth it. I'm also disappointed that we don't know how or why Tigris went from being a close cousin to Snow to eventually becoming a rebel sympathizer???? That's the one loose end that bothers me. There were a lot of characters in this book (with a lot of strange names) so it did get pretty confusing at times, but overall I really liked Jessup, Lysistrata, our girl Lucy Gray, and really sympathized with Sejanus. It was interesting to see the development of the games from such an early time, and learning about the actual creation of them was a really impactful moment in the end. Part 3: The Peacekeeper really made everything come together, and I loved (and hated) what happened between Snow, Sejanus, and Lucy Gray. In a morbid way, I wish that there was more of this behaviour throughout the first 3 quarters of the book because it's more how I was expecting Snow to act, but then again this book makes sense in the way that we first see the people around him who ultimately influenced him to get to the point where we eventually see him as President Snow. I loved the songs but had mixed

feelings about the connections that they had to the original trilogy, in addition to the katniss plant and district 12 focus, because on one hand I kind of hate the fact that this is suggesting that a big part of the reason why Snow hated Katniss and needed her dead was because she reminded him so much of Lucy Gray. But then at the same time, I also *love* the fact that Snow heard these songs from Lucy Gray at a younger time and that 65 years later he hears them again from our girl on fire because it basically gives Katniss the power to *really* mock President Snow without even knowing it. The hanging scenes were done really well with the eeriness coming from the birds and Lucy Gray writing the song. I think those scenes will be super cool and heartbreaking to see in the eventual movie that I'm very excited about. Lucy Gray was definitely a standout character that I loved, and she was manipulated by Snow so I can't blame her for loving him, but wow I hated how possessive he immediately was with her. (Which, again, showed that he's a villain.) Despite its flaws (and they certainly make it a difficult read), and the many negative reviews that I've also seen, I'm so glad that I decided to stick with reading this book to decide how I liked it myself. I'm just going to hype the ending forever because I loved it.” amanda's review. In: Goodreads, 22.05.2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2861380742> [07.06.2023]

“Listen, I hate President Snow as much as the next person.

But SNOW. FUCKING. LANDS. ON. TOP.

This is actually brilliant. Like genius. Critical, and scathing and thought provoking.

Sprinkled with moments where your jaw just quietly drops in shock and pain but you can't do anything except keep on reading.

This book is hypnotic. It had an unputdownable quality I'm still unable to quite put my finger on.

Hats off, this is how you prequel.

The only reason I took off a star was because of the rushed ending. I would've easily read 200 or 300 pages more if it meant the ending was handled as beautifully as the rest of the book was.” Mariah's review. In: Goodreads, 09.06.2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2861741205> [07.06.2023]

“Let’s get one thing straight: **Coriolanus Snow is an asshole**. He’s an evil, ministry-loving, family-disowning, power-hungry moron and this books does not try to convince the reader otherwise. If anything, I came out of this book with a more complete understanding of Snow’s character, coupled with a more complete loathing for him. But what this book does, which is honestly incredible, is that even though you never warm up to Snow (get it?), you end up rooting for him. You know that he doesn’t deserve fame, or power, but you want him to be the kid who impresses the Gamemakers the most, and who mentors his tribute to win the Hunger Games, even while at the same time wanting him to just run away and never come back to terrorize Panem as president as he is destined to do.

spoilers for the original *Hunger Games* trilogy

The Ballad of Songbirds an Snakes is centered around the 10th Hunger Games. These games are different than what the reader already knows: rather than being showered with riches before the Games, the tributes are treated brutally and left in a cage to wait for the day when they will be stuck into an old arena and told to fight. 24 students from the prestigious academy, Coriolanus Snow included, are awarded the all-new positions of mentors to the tributes. Snow is, rather predictably considering the original trilogy, given the girl tribute from District 12, which he considers a disgrace until the tribute turns out to be Lucy Grey, a charismatic girl who makes the Capitol fall in love with her through her music. So basically, Snow has a crisis: he supports the Hunger Games, but he doesn’t want this girl to die.

The Hunger Games, with it’s iconic characters, the spectacle of the games, and heroine that you could always root for, was a book that you could read and tell that it was destined for fame. The Hunger Games in this book do not in any way resemble the gilded spectacle that they would become 64 years later, and though Lucy Grey could be iconic in another light, the way in which she was introduced in this book, told from Snow’s perspective, does not set her up to be so. Whereas in the original series, the reader found themselves drawn into the games, and the action-packed conflict between the Capitol and the Districts, this book is centered around the conflict of human nature, and frankly, that’s not entirely as exciting.

The constant suspense felt during the first book of the original *Hunger Games* ebbs and flows, sometimes present and sometimes nowhere to be seen. But, in my opinion, **these differences work in favor of this book, and the message which it is sending.**

The Games themselves aren't the only aspect of Panem which is different during this time period. Gone are the riches of the Capitol which are shoved in the faces of the Districts during Katniss' time. Instead, many people in the Capitol, Snow included, are struggling to rebuild after the war which ended just ten years prior. Although the poverty in the Capitol is nothing like that in the Districts, Snow still often struggles to get enough food and his cousin, Tigris (yes, Tigris!) struggles to raise enough money for the three of them in their family. Compared to the high-tech creations of 64 years later, this is a future which is only separated from the world we know by a different government and some genetic engineering advances. The connection to the present world is emphasized through music, and some folk tunes which are known now. There are also, newly, tantalizing hints about a society outside of Panem, north of District 12. Are these just early hints of District 13, or is there really a civilization, possibly a continuity of a government in the world today, north of Panem?

For the entirety of the book, the question is bounced around as we meet new characters with different morals and backgrounds: **whose fault is the Hunger Games?** Throughout the book, Snow claims that it could never be his fault, of course. He is just a child, doing what his superiors tell him to in mentoring Lucy Grey for a fight to the death.

There are so many ways in which this book could have gone horribly wrong, and luckily I do not believe that it did any of these. However, there were times at which the plot felt rather scattered and unfocused, as it somewhat switched course halfway through and did not have the strong structure of the original *Hunger Games*, more of the loose string of events reminiscent of *Mockingjay*. This was my main issue with the book, because although this did not lose my interest, it does bug me when books are a little bit all over the place. It also took a little while to get moving, and I had to press through the first few chapters to get to anything interesting, but it picked up.

Overall, none of this took away from my enjoyment of the book, and I would highly recommend this to anyone who read the original series, even if they did not enjoy it. This book is clearly in the same world, yet it is very different from the original so even if you did not like the original series, it is possible that you could enjoy this book. 100% recommend!!!” anya's review. In: Goodreads, 17.06.2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2861405523> [07.06.2023]

“2/5 ☐☐ I wanna cry I didn't like it I feel like I'm betraying did you hear that? ... That was my heart .. it cracked ” booknator's review. In: Goodreads, 14.06.2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2861429683> [07.06.2023]

“Want to read

She's gonna break my heart all over again, and I'm going to let her.

HAVE I LEARNED NOTHING FROM MOCKINGJAY????” Nicki Chapelway's review. In: Goodreads, 29.02.2020. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2861432042> [07.06.2023]

“Who else is using this as an excuse to reread THG?

Everybody's screaming about how their 14 yr old self is screaming...

... then there's me

..... guys I read this for the first time last year.....” Ace's review. In: Goodreads, 20.01.2021. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2861846989> [07.06.2023]

“I tried to read this one but I just couldn't get through the first part. I revisited via audiobook and I was able to get through it. This was a struggle for multiple reasons but now I want to go back and read the whole Hunger Games

series again.” Kat's review.. In: Goodreads, 20.03.2021. Available from:
[:https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3002372864](https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3002372864) [07.06.2023]

“i did *truly* find the nods to the original trilogy fun. finally finding out the origin of the hanging tree song, why snow despised katniss so much from the get-go, how certain features of the games were implemented, etc. was really interesting. that being said, i've seen a number of reviews say that this read like fan fiction, and i honestly kind of agree. the way that every single loose end from the original story was tied up felt a lot like fan service to me, and while as a fan of the original trilogy i gladly ate that shit up, i don't think any of it was a needed addition to the overall world.

- snow's character felt like an afterthought in his own book?? I was surprised by what a passive protagonist he was for the majority of the story, and he lacked the detail and nuance that would have made this a compelling character study. while i liked that we got to see how easily he was able to manipulate others from the start, his overall transition from the little, privileged weasel of the first two parts to the actual villain in part three was entirely abrupt and unsatisfying.

- the pacing of this was also wonky as heck. the first 450 pages were moving at the pace of a snail (that's a fact, not a complaint. i enjoyed the slower bits more) compared with the breakneck pace of the final 60 pages, i got whiplash.

- the ending (no spoilers) but while i thought snow's portion wrapped up way too quickly just as he was getting interesting, there was enough left hanging with *cough* other characters *cough* that i truly wouldn't be surprised if we got a sequel to this story, and idk how i feel about that.

not sure what else to say....basically, unpacking more of panem's history was an ambitious idea on collins' part, and i think it could have been done well (maybe as part of a collection of novellas?) but, this book was just far too long and failed to strike a good balance between snow's story and the exposition of the early games.”

Kat's review In: Goodreads, 12.07.2022. Available from:
<https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3395346579> [07.06.2023]

“I was craving a genuine villain origin story for Snow, and the details just weren’t there for me. Other than the symbolism and irony Collins inserted there is not much this book contributed to the overall Hunger Games concept. I could have lived without it. To quote the lovely Merphy Napier, “This book is boring and predictable.” I guessed so much of what happened and felt so disinterested.

The pacing was also messy. There were many moments of development and then sporadic action that felt unearned. Much of the plot also felt too convenient to me and it wasn’t believable enough. I wanted more grit and genuine evil from Snow, instead of a weird romance that felt like a pathetic attempt for readers to have sympathy for him. If there’s a sequel, there is definitely room to expound upon Snow.

This book feels like an attempt to tie a bow that just looks all messy, which could be the ultimate intent Collins was going for. Unfortunately, for how complex of a role Snow serves in the main trilogy, I expected more out of his backstory.”

Catherine’s review. In: Goodreads, 16.01.2022. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2861769058> [07.06.2023]

“Damn this book was loooong....

I read fast but most things were so boring though i have to give it to suzanne collins, she really showed the transformation of the innocent, "could never hurt a fly" boy to a vicious, cunning man.

I was invested in the love story, even knowing it was doomed to fail (considering who president snow is). Though it’s shocking how closely linked he was with katniss in so many different ways . It’s like she was made to taunt him and remind him of his past.

For the people that say that this book only humanizes a villain and tyrant, you are probably not a fan of psychology. It is the same things we do with serial killer stories, we get the behind of why this happens so we know how to crush it and recognize it.

With president snow, it's so intricate to see all of thoughts and action that make him a murderer and someone cruel. There is no rationalizing his actions, it's just seeing a glimpse into his history.

However, at part 3 I kinda lost my interest cause it was dragged out, he became too cruel for me to suffer while everyone around him trusted him blindly. The romance was so cute to see, even if toxic and for selfish reasons.”Thea’s Reading World 💛’s review. In: Goodreads, 06.09.2022. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2862498873> [07.06.2023]

“always trust your gut.

for example, here is my initial note on this book:

do i want to read this book?

no.

well, i don't think so.

okay i'm going to leave this here just in case

and if i had just gone with that feeling and absolutely sprinted in the opposite direction, we wouldn't be here right now.

writing a rant review about a book whose main crimes are being boring and not as good as the actual series it's a prequel of.

see? even my complaints about it aren't interesting.

like, for example, this million page long book would be more like 40 if you took out every usage of the protagonists' incredibly long names (coriolanus and lucy gray, which they say CONSTANTLY and always IN FULL), plus the words cabbage soup, for some reason.

if you took out every reference to the title we wouldn't have a book at all.

and, for another example, what if i told you this was one of the suckiest romances of all time, so awful i am forced to use the already made up term "sucky" to the fullest extent english grammar will allow me. a love story between two boring

teens, one who is classist and misogynistic and hateful and boring, and one who is poor and a woman and saccharine and also boring.

what if, hypothetically, the lucy gray character's main personality trait is that she writes and performs songs, and what if the songs are unbearable and corny even as everything else in the book rides on our ability to believe they, for lack of a better word, slay?

what if everything that made the hunger games so appealing and well-done - the action, the satire, the quiet and subtle moments of revolution - did not exist here?

and have you considered if the whole thing were so boring it feels like it could be charged in international court?

yeah.

not good.

bottom line: get in, loser. we're going to trust our instincts and avoid unnecessary additions to beloved series” emma's review In: Goodreads, 22.12.2022. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3344906122> [08.06.2023]

Най-нови:

“fueron las 600 páginas más aburridas que leí en mi vida” nazzareno 's review. In: Goodreads, 14.03.2023. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2861373316> [08.06.2023]

“(30/4/23) putting this up to five stars now... I don't think people got this when it came out but upon reread. Jesus Christ she did it again

IT WAS SO GOOD. Collins is a master of symbolism and foreshadowing, and the little allusions to the original series and how it all links is super well done. The Games originally being super primitive and looked down upon compared to the lavish way it is in the main series was kinda startling, but Snow becoming a game maker at the end made total sense. There were enough things in it to allude to the original series, but not too many to make it clunky or like she was trying to cling to

the original relevance. Perhaps a few too many characters with too-complicated names, but that lessened once we left the Capitol.

Snow's arc was very subtle, but very well done, you don't realise the extent to which he was manipulating everyone until it's too late; idk if he even registers it either. Sejanus's death was VERY jarring, horrific really, and it kinda marked the end of Snow's spiral into insanity, even though it'd been a long time coming-- it was set up really well. The bit at the end in the epilogue where he basically manipulated the Plinths into giving him everything was really shocking and gave scope to how he really controls people, as well as the way he murdered the Dean.

I'm disappointed we didn't get to find out more about his proper rise to power, but from this and the OG series you can piece it together. I guess the mouth sores are from rat poison, seeing as Finnick said it was the same poison he killed his enemies with, and it would make sense. I wish I knew what happened to Tigris to turn her against him, though-- like what was the tipping point? There were a couple of loose threads but not too bad, considering.

Characters were all good, though I'd have liked a little more vivacity from Lucy in places, but Snow himself, Ma, Tigris and Sejanus were really well done. The repeated motifs and things were also rly well done and effective.

Maybe the plot was a bit jumpy in places but not too bad. Overall, good!”
Kate's review. In: Goodreads, 01.05.2023. Available from:
<https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3216431421> [08.06.2023]

“Suzanne Collins is a fucking mastermind. The premise of the book was amazing on its own, but I think it's such a good prequel because of how much this book adds to the original trilogy. It successfully builds off what we already know and love, while giving us an inside look at the creation of the games and the lines Coriolanus Snow crosses into evil.

President Snow's backstory was clever and haunting. Seeing the Hunger Games come together and watching the seeds being planted for Katniss's story was everything I needed and more. I also love Sejanus Plinth with my whole heart and

soul. Lucy Gray was also fascinating, and I cannot stop screaming about how much I love her impact on the series as a whole.

Absolutely loved this and I can't wait for the movie!” Ethan's review. In: Goodreads, 06.05.2023. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2861429547> [07.06.2023]

“So after quite some time, I've finished this book. And what a hardship it was, at that.

Giving this book a 2.5 stars. It was ok. Here is what I have to say:

Part 1 and part 2 were amazing. It had everything from her Hunger Games novels: suspense, cliffhangers, action, etc. Plus Suzanne Collins superb writing was imprinted on it.

Part 3, on the other hand, was its downfall. I had a hard time keeping up. I was less engaged to story by the minute and I couldn't care less about anyone. I felt its contents were just fillers, boring and added nothing to the story at some points. Only almost by the end of it, it started to draw my interest again.

Coriolanus Snow was inconsistent and annoying at most. As for Lucy Gray, Suzanne Collins fell short with her arc development. I think it could've been explored more thoroughly. I really liked Sejanus character tho; he remained consistent, well-constructed, and believable.

I really tried to like this book in all its forms but I just couldn't. Sorry Suzanne Collins, not your best work. I was so bummed.

19/5/2023 - edit

On further notice and after reading this for the second time in preparation for the movie coming out this november, I'm deciding to modify my rating to a 3.5 stars. Whilst it had some weak points (i.e the slow pacing sometimes) and not being nearly as exciting and catchy as the previous three Hunger Games books, I actually enjoyed this book this second time around and appreciated more what Suzanne Collins was trying to convey and achieve with this book.” Emmanuel Guzman's review. In: Goodreads, 20.05.2023. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3193690815> [07.06.2023]

“did i skim/possibly not at all read the last 100 pages? maybe. what's it to you for some reason i thought i'd actually like this book now that i don't skim by default anymore, but it still fell really flat for me. collins' writing style is so much better suited to action and quick, gritty first-person imo, and a lot of the appeal of the original trilogy was the worldbuilding. because these books are so much more political than the originals, there was so much telling instead of showing and it made the whole book feel really sluggish overall. i never got invested in any of the characters, so the plot didn't really matter to me either. the way the games were written were also very...dry? it might've been interesting to have the pov switch between lucy and snow. idk it just didn't at all grab my attention like the original duology did. but i'm still going to watch the movie ig

Original (6/3/20):

Remember the Hunger Games, the original trilogy? The fast-paced, action-packed books about everyone's favorite heroine, Katniss Everdeen, the fiery and resilient underdog who fought for her family and the rights of the oppressed?

Well...this is not like the Hunger Games.

This is just a generally slow book that (as I said before) had either no climax or at least four. The pacing was so off and it felt like the book should've been cut off a lot earlier.

Reading this book is like watching the Star Wars prequels knowing what Anakin becomes (and, yes, I'm going to use that comparison until the day I die). We know what Snow turns out to be: the ruthless, conniving tyrant who Katniss swears she will kill. In this book, however, he's an ambitious and charming 18-year-old (who is even described as "gorgeous" by another character).

This book wasn't written to make us forgive Snow, in my opinion. It merely shows us why and how he became the man we see in the originals.

Lucy Gray Baird. I love that name. And I loved the character. She was bold and her songs were pretty good. Until there were SO MANY OF THEM. I sort of started skimming through them after a certain point. This book is a MUSICAL. It felt like every two chapters had a song and if they ever made a movie, it would be a musical. You think I'm exaggerating? Read the book.

I was addicted to this book for the first half-ish. And then it just went downhill. The plot, the characters, all of it. The ending was so confusing, it might've rivaled School for Good and Evil's ending. The second half seemed like unnecessary fluff that I honestly didn't care about - it was boring and confusing. But the ending? It seemed like it was trying to be a plot twist but just wasn't cutting it. A lot of people said it was “explosive” and the only good part, but I was so lost.

I did really like the first section of the book until after the games. I did really like Lucy. I'm looking forward to the movie and even though this definitely isn't as good as the original three, I am GOING to reread it and try to make more sense of it.”Ellie's review. In: Goodreads, 22.05.2023. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/3058599686> [08.06.2023]

“AHHHHHH I JUST WATCHED THE TRAILER FOR THE MOVIE AND IT'S GOING TO BE AMAZING OMGEEEEEE

I'M JUST GOING TO QUIETLY OBSESS OVER THIS UNTIL IT COMES OUT IN NOVEMBER
HKHLHHLHKJLJSKKS

📖 original review (upon reread) 📖 01/04/23

This book is an evil masterpiece, you can't change my mind Coriolanus's villainous fall is terrifying and I love Lucy Gray with everything I have.

And yes, I totally sobbed just as much as I sobbed the first time around. ” ✨
lydia °+ ✨ {hiatus}'s review. In: Goodreads, 16.05.2023. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/4073348387> [08.06.2023]

“assez déçue par la fin, qui selon moi a été bâclée

des références aux Hungers Games que l'on connaît un peu trop insistantes pour faire naturelles et des personnages pour lesquels je n'ai pas été foncièrement attachée

même si retrouver l'univers était quelque peu satisfaisant et que j'en ai apprécié la lecture, je ne peux pas nier le fait que l'histoire manquait d'action, de plots (je

voulais avoir au moins une réaction avec la mâchoire au sol et le fameux : C'ÉTAIT ÇA DEPUIS LE DÉBUT !!? » mais non, même pas

pareil pour Tigris : ?;? where is the explanation of her downfall in the Hunger Games ?; TELL ME

bref un peu saoulée alors que c'était super prometteur” Mathixde's review. In: Goodreads, 22.05.2023. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/2899603326> [08.06.2023]

“Snow lands on top. This is the origin story we all needed. I have seen negative reviews questioning why she would write an origin story on the most hated character. Two things.

1) Snow is instrumental in the development and evolution of the Hunger Games as we know them.

2) I have always been curious about his background and how he came to be. Snow's absolute resolve to a path of power and his lack of empathy are compelling. The bit where he considers Sejanus's ma's cookies. (jaw on floor)

This book answered questions I had about the Hunger Games and the districts. I found the evolution of the games to be fascinating. The way the tributes used to be treated vs the spectacle and opulence we see in the original trilogy. The introduction of sponsors and how the designation of mentors to the tributes evolved. We are introduced to one of the most horrifically cruel game makers in the history of the games.

“There is a point to everything or nothing at all, depending on your worldview.”

-Dr. Volumnia Gaul

“What happened in the arena? That's humanity undressed. The tributes. And you, too. How quickly civilization disappears. All your fine manners, education, family background, everything you pride yourself on, stripped away in the blink of an eye, revealing everything you actually are. A boy with a club who beats another boy to death. That's mankind in its natural state.”

-Dr. Volumnia Gaul

That doctor scares the beep outta me. Sejanus is our moral compass and has some of my favorite lines in the book!

“You've no right to starve people, to punish them for no reason. No right to take away their life and freedom. Those are things everyone is born with, and they're not yours for the taking. Winning a war doesn't give you that right. Having more weapons doesn't give you that right. Being from the Capitol doesn't give you that right. Nothing does.”

-Sejanus Plinth

Overall, this was a treat and a very satisfying beginning to the world of Panem.

****TO SUZANNE COLLINS****

Thank you for this rich history in Panem. Please write a series about all of the victors.

The Winner's Circle ☐☐ potential title?

I would love a book dedicated to Finnick.

The way he deals in secrets. What all those secrets must be. What life in the capitol must be like for him.

This line of thought only makes me curious about all of the victors of the Hunger Games.” Cecelia | hotforbooks's review. In: Goodreads 04.03.2023. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/review/show/4931696383> [07.06.2023]

Коментари в Library Thing:

“Suzanne Collins returns to the world of 'The Hunger Games' to tell the story of young Coriolanus Snow. For those who don't remember, that's Donald Sutherland. The original trilogy captivated me when I first read it, but I had my doubts about a prequel after all these years. This is partly because these books don't continue to resonate with me the way some other YA powerhouses have. Nostalgia is a

powerful thing, however, so expect this one to be on the bestseller list for some time.

This was a fast read, even at 500+ pages, and there was some pleasure in seeing the world that had only been viewed through Katniss' limited gaze with greater clarity. The problem I ultimately had with this is the problem that hits a lot of prequels: this story had a foregone conclusion. The story has to have an interesting journey on top of the plot. Was the goal to humanize Snow? To reinforce the message of the original trilogy? To provide an alternative to the increasingly lampooned Katniss model of YA heroine in Lucy Gray? Having finished this...I still can't give you those answers.

I'm rating this as only OK because we didn't see any transformation of Snow. Cunning sociopathic person wins the day may be realistic, but it wasn't riveting as presented here. Lucy Gray is only a cypher because we never hear her perspective, and what we do see is from Snow's eyes, so.... Most importantly, I didn't buy the moral complications presented to the reader. Right and wrong were pretty clear and there was little or no real internal struggle on the part of the characters. That was a defining highlight of the original books. 'Ballad' succeeds only in being a return to a familiar world and by filling in gaps in the timeline of the series. If you liked the original trilogy, you'll find something in this book. Just don't expect the moon.

On the plus side, many bookstores got Mockingjay/Snake iron-on patches so if you pre-ordered a copy with them you get one for free. Check with your local - they may have extra patches that are first come/first served if you didn't preorder!” ManWithAnAgenda's review. In: LibraryThing, 19.05.2020. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23367868/reviews/183552090> [07.06.2023]

“Coriolanus Snow endured hunger, deprivation, and the loss of both parents during the Rebel siege on the Capitol. His cousin’s bargaining abilities at the Black

Market enabled them to survive, but the Snow family fortune was destroyed. Coriolanus is determined to keep it secret that the Snows, one of the Capitol’s Old Guard families, is poor.

His favorite professor at the Academy was able to get him assigned to one of the tributes for the upcoming Hunger Games as a student mentor, so he has a chance to vie for a University scholarship. Coriolanus knows winning the Games is his only hope to having a future, and is desperate to win. When he’s assigned Lucy Gray Baird from District 12 he’s disappointed because he’d hoped for a strong boy, however, her musical abilities and joie de vivre help to change his mind.

As he spends time with Lucy Gray, he begins to think of her as a person instead of as a tribute. His determination to protect her from the other tributes, and to win, begins to override rational thoughts until the lines between right and wrong get blurred. As time goes on Coriolanus’ determination to always win, and to always come out on top, will forever change their lives.

When I was given the opportunity to read this ARC, I wondered if it would be as interesting as the other books in The Hunger Games series because, after all, it IS about the very evil President Snow. However, not only is it exciting, but I found myself feeling sorry for Coriolanus. SORRY for HIM?! I can hear gasps echoing around the world, but let me preface that comment. I felt sorry for him in the BEGINNING and MIDDLE of the book, but definitely not by the end. Make sure to read the book to find out why.

I’m now off to reread The Hunger Games series and decipher clues revealed in “The ballad of songbirds and snakes.” I won’t be surprised if Collins writes another follow up to the Coriolanus Snow saga.

Highly recommended for ages 14 and older.

I received a digital advance reading copy of this book from the publisher in exchange for an honest review.” sunshinealma’s review. In: LibraryThing, 23.05.2020. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23367868/reviews/183842471> [07.06.2023]

“I wasn’t sure about this book going in: why would we want to read the backstory of the loathsome President Snow? But Collins has carried it off well here,

and certainly made me want to keep reading until the very end. And thankfully it's not just Snow's backstory she provides, too, but also more about the roots of Panem, the Hunger Games, and the mockingjays.” JBD1's review. In: LibraryThing, 25.05.2020. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23367868/reviews/183649781> [07.06.2023]

“The best description for this book/series in 10 words or less:

“Young man faced with poverty fights between right and wrong.”

I was stoked to find out that Suzanne Collins was writing another book in The Hunger Games series even if it was a prequel. I didn't know exactly what to expect when it comes to this book, but overall I really enjoyed it. It wasn't as good as The Hunger Games trilogy but it was definitely worth the 10-year wait. It is and should be read as its own book rather than as part of The Hunger Games series.

I loved the angle that Collins took for The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes. You only see President Snow as this heartless and cold leader in The Hunger Games trilogy, but Collins did an excellent job in really humanizing President Snow as an 18-year old student who goes by Coriolanus. You can see his personal struggles outside of the Hunger Games, which makes you want to continue reading and get the answer as to why he became such a heartless and cold antagonist that you see him be in the trilogy.

When I first read the synopsis, I was really interested to see how Snow was a mentor to tributes when he was born as a Capitol citizen. It makes sense that since it's only the 10th Hunger Games that it still is in the experimental phase. It's interesting to see how the Hunger Games morphed into what they are in the trilogy and how Coriolanus Snow had a hand in a lot of it pretty early on. You can clearly see the struggle of young minds (not just Coriolanus) wrestling with and trying to figure out what is deserved versus being cruel.

The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes also doesn't disappoint in all the symbolism and irony through the use of Greek mythology, especially when it comes to the characters.

Whether you read The Hunger Games series or not you will not be missing out because you don't know you're missing it. If you do read both the prequel and the trilogy you.

Lots of questions get answered in this novel such as the following:

- Who started the Hunger Games? How they really started? Why it's called the Hunger Games?
- Why is Snow so obsessed with those roses?
- What is the real meaning behind the mockingjays?
- Why Snow hates Katniss Everdeen so much?
- Where do the songs Katniss sings come from? What are their real meanings?
- Who really is Tigris?
- Finally, how did Snow come to power? (This one you can figure out based on Snow's actions in this novel)

This novel also opens the door to more questions that can be answered in another novel, such as Tigris and Snow's fall out. If I was Collins, I would definitely write a prequel with Haymitch and incorporate the fall out there for reasons I can't explain without spoiling the pieces of The Hunger Games trilogy.

Whether you're reading this before The Hunger Games series or after, I suggest you read another read-through of the trilogy because there are so many different tidbits that are put into The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes that you only see in The Hunger Games trilogy. This is definitely worth the read!” Marilyn95's review. In: LibraryThing, 25.05.2020. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23367868/reviews/184304629> [07.06.2023]

“WOW! I didn't know if I would love this but I was hooked in the first chapter. I was drawn back in so quickly it was like I never left Panem! I didn't think I would care for a story that centered on Snow the future president; but really it was fascinating. He's a teenager when the 10th Hunger Games takes place and he's assigned as a mentor to a girl from District 12. Readers get SO MUCH backstory on the games, the war, and the slow and steady rise of the capital. Snow is from a

great family but dirt poor - having his champion, Lucy Gray, win the Hunger Games could secure his spot in University - tuition free. Snow always land on top. Things get a lot more complicated when he starts to fall for Lucy Gray, how could they ever make romance work though - she's from the districts?! Filled with so many unforgettable characters; this book will make readers want to re-read the entire trilogy. My true rating 4.5. Excellent, unexpected prequel”! ecataldi's review. In: LibraryThing, 04.06.2020. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23367868/reviews/184531846> [07.06.2023]

“Suzanne Collins has done it again. In this book, we are introduced to the back story of the villain from the Hunger Games president Snow from when he was a teenager. Knowing what we know now about his future, you read this anticipating something awful to happen in his life to turn the decent teenager into the menacing figure in the Hunger Games series. I was doubtful that the book would be any good and thought that Collins was just "cashing in" on previous success, however, the story has enough in it to keep even the most avid fan entertained.

In this prequel, we learn about some of the origins of the Hunger Games as Snow, as a final year student is paired up to mentor a tribute from District 11 called Lucy Gray who sings beautifully and wins his heart. We also learn the backstory of the origins of the genetically modified creatures we see in the trilogy and learn about the class system that exists that divides the people in the Capitol from those in the Districts. An engaging prequel. “nicsreads's review. In: LibraryThing, 10.06.2020. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23367868/reviews/184808526> [07.06.2023]

“What’s there to say other than if I’d read this first I never have continued on to read The Hunger Games. In fact, I doubt I'd have even finished it. But since I'd read The Hunger Games trilogy before this one I trudged on, thinking the writing, the plot, and the characterizations were bound to get better. They did not.” wandaly's review. In: LibraryThing, 15.06.2020. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23367868/reviews/185078194> [07.06.2023]

“Pandemic read. The backstory for Snow.” bookczuk’s review. In: LibraryThing, 20.12.2021. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23367868/reviews/193887002> [07.06.2023]

“The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes by Suzanne Collins tells the story of Coriolanus Snow who grows up to be President Snow in the The Hunger Games trilogy. It’s been many years since I read the three books or watched the movies in the original trilogy. Sequels, prequels, and accompaniment stories rarely ever captivate as much as the original. That is certainly true of this one. It does not capture the uniqueness or the intensity of The Hunger Games. Am I glad I read it? Yes. Will I likely follow along? Yes, for the story and for the trip down memory lane. Will it have the same impact as the original? No.” njmom3’s review. In: LibraryThing, 20.12.2021. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23367868/reviews/194373755> [07.06.2023]

“I knew this would be harder to read than the other hunger games...how can one turn one of the most vile characters in literature, Coriolanus Snow, into an engaging protagonist? Suzanne Collins continues her mastery at letting the readers inside her characters’ heads, but that just means that we can clearly see the cold calculations and brainwashed analysis in Snow’s brain compared to the kindness and empathy that comes out of his mouth. It’s the worst. The only character he treats with honest emotion and love is his cousin Tigris, but from the final book in the trilogy we know that something had to have happened along the way to make him cast her off as well and leave her to suffer. If you liked the Hunger Games trilogy than I would recommend reading this book. It fills in historical gaps and paints a vivid, though horrific, picture of how the Hunger Games transformed from something universally disliked if not outright despised, into casual revelry for a capital that lost its soul along the way. Just don’t expect to enjoy it.” sanyamakadi’s review. In: LibraryThing, 02.02.2021. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23367868/reviews/195990739> [07.06.2023]

“I am speechless after the ending...”

Normally, I don’t like when authors add prequels, spin-offs, etc. to an already-existing series, but Suzanne Collins did very well with this one.” Akacya’s

review. In: LibraryThing, 28.02.2021. Available from:
<https://www.librarything.com/work/23367868/reviews/197081500> [07.06.2023]

“The world of the Hunger Games is so compelling that I could read 20 more books about it. However, this book is a villain story and Snow is so unredeemable that his motives felt flat. The forced connections/callbacks made to the original trilogy were also awkward at times. I still think this book is worth reading if you want to be back in the world of the Hunger Games and learn about how it started.”
thereserose5's review. In: LibraryThing, 03.03.2021. Available from:
<https://www.librarything.com/work/23367868/reviews/197229595> [07.06.2023]

“I was looking forward to reading this Prequel novel set in the world of the Hunger Games, hoping for some more explanation of how and why the Hunger Games were established and some back-story on President Snow. The book did deliver on that, but seemed somewhat dissatisfying. I can't really explain it. However, it was interesting to re-read the original trilogy with the events of this book in mind, as there were some pretty neat easter eggs.”
EmScape's review. In: LibraryThing, 14.03.2021. Available from:
<https://www.librarything.com/work/23367868/reviews/197673601> [07.06.2023]

“The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes takes place 64 years prior to the Hunger Games of Katniss' time. Coriolanus Snow (who later becomes President Snow) is 18 years old and living in the Capitol. His family has fallen upon hard times following the war and the death of his parents. The 10th Hunger Games is about to take place, and he and some of his peers have been offered the opportunity to become mentors in the Games. Coriolanus is assigned the female tribute from District 12. Though initially disappointed, he eventually looks upon this as an opportunity to bring respect back to the Snow name, especially after meeting his tribute, the charismatic Lucy Gray Baird.

Though this book has a somewhat different feel than the original Hunger Games trilogy, it was nice to return to Suzanne Collins and the world of Panem. It

was initially hard to reconcile the Snow of the original trilogy to the teenage Snow of this book. I wanted to hate him but I couldn't. He was actually a fairly decent guy once upon a time. The book is more or less divided into two halves, the first being the events of the 10th Hunger Games and the second being the events that occur afterwards. While I enjoyed revisiting the actual events of the Hunger Games again, they were much less refined and they lacked the creativity of the later Games. However, we did get to see how some of the qualities of the games evolved into what they were in later years.

Suzanne Collins tried to make Snow appear more humane by incorporating the relationship between he and Lucy Gray. I bought into this up to a point. But I didn't care for the second half of the book nearly as much as the first, and I really didn't like the way his character evolved almost overnight. It felt too sudden and choppy and unrealistic, and while I didn't exactly dislike the ending, I didn't like the way Collins fleshed it out to get there. It just felt unfulfilling.

I didn't dislike this book. It's hard to write a prequel that lives up to its original series, and I don't feel that this one necessarily deserved some of the bad reviews that it got. There were parts that were lacking, but I did enjoy it for the most part.” indygo88's review. In: LibraryThing, 14.03.2021. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23367868/reviews/183650025> [07.06.2023]

“The Highly anticipated next book by Suzanne Collins? Or the prequel nobody asked for? Like most people I absolutely loved the Hunger Games when they came out. Although I have to be honest, I did kind of lost my focus around book 3 at the time. Having read the original trilogy I was looking forward to seeing what this author had in store for this world.

In this book we follow Coriolanus Snow, Future president of Panem. Only in this book we follow him in his teen year. Long before he becomes president. It's the tenth annual Hunger Games and this year they are introducing the mentors as part of the games. Coriolanus gets chosen to become one and we follow him as he navigates his school, mentor and love life.

I was really looking forward to this book. I knew Suzanne Collins could write a good book so I had high hopes. Seeing people online being disappointed in the discovery that Coriolanus would be the mean character wasn't a concern I had. I was pretty confident that the author would be able to write a good story how this antagonist came to be. I have to say I'm kind of disappointed where the book went halfway through.

Let me start with the good bits. I really liked the worldbuilding. I had no problem imagining the different surroundings and places where the story took place. I really liked that we got to see more of the Capital from a different inside perspective. The way that this story took place right after the war was also a really cool setup. The fact that they were still trying to figure out how the Hunger Games should be played and what it would take to make them “work” was quite interesting.

And now for the bad bits. I hated Coriolanus. Although I can see how we are supposed to hate him I couldn't find one bit charming or even remotely relatable. Also, can I just say that I absolutely hate that I had to read the name coriolANUS like 500 times? The way he starts of as a teenager living in poor conditions to becoming what he becomes at the end of the book wasn't as interesting because you already know the outcome. The book also had a very weird setup in my opinion. I feel like the three parts this book had would be better if they would be shuffled and rearranged. Which is a weird thing to say. The way how part 3 was written made it feel like more of a setup for a whole different story. Also, the chapters had such “cliffhangers” that after a while you kind of get used to them cause after reading “and then, a bomb went off” you can't really care at all anymore. For it being such a mixed bag, I have to say that I can't give it more than 3 stars. It being more of a 2,5 than a 3 tbh.

“If you want to read a good dystopian I would recommend you stick with the original trilogy and don't pick up this book.” luclicious's review. In: LibraryThing, 20.09.2021. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23367868> [07.06.2023]

“This is a prequel to the Hunger Games giving the origin story of President Snow, and I read it quickly, and enjoyed it, but it does feel like slightly ret-conned Hunger Games fanfic. Snow is made to be a mentor for the Hunger Games when he is a child of about the same age as the victims, and falls in love with a covey girl who is the tribute for district 12. But in the end, his longing for power and success in the capital is too great for him to chose love and a life of poverty.

Hunger Games fans will enjoy visiting lots of places from the original trilogy (the cabin in the woods, the meadow, the Hob), although more cynical Hunger Games fans will think it is amazingly unlikely that Katniss's nemesis actually spent his childhood wandering around her home town.

I am not Roma, and so am probably not best placed to comment on whether the covey are a good attempt to introduce more minority charactors and a more diverse world, or another set of stereotypes about travelling people who sing beautifully and tragically die young, It seems worth considering as a question though.” atreic's review. In: LibraryThing, 14.02.2022. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23367868/reviews/212646065> [07.06.2023]

“It's sneaky and interesting, and Suzanne Collins has a twisted brain. For me, it was a fascinating look into the early days of the Hunger Games, before the spectacle of the ones from the original trilogy.

**** SPOILERS BELOW ****

That insight into where everything started, coupled with the slow descent into his President Snow persona, made this book decidedly uncomfortable to read. I am one of those readers who instantly identifies with a main character, no matter how different they are, so "seeing" Snow slowly, then very quickly, descend into a rotten human being was absorbing, but ultimately left me with a bad taste in my mouth. There is no hopeful note here, like in the original trilogy, but I don't think Ms. Collins was ever going to get hopeful out of this story.” Ahsoka3230's review. In: LibraryThing, 15.02.2022. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23367868/reviews/212710483> [07.06.2023]

“The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes by Suzanne Collins (2020) (3 stars)

This was a prequel story to the events that happened in the Hunger Games Trilogy, set some 60 odd years before we meet Katniss Everdeen in that series. It is the prequel of the villain in those stories, President Snow, so from the beginning you know that this story cannot have a happy ending because it's the story of the evil guy that helped make the Hunger Games stories so horrifying. Why then would anyone want to read it? Good question. After I read Songbirds and Snakes, I had to watch the movies all over again since it had been a few years since I'd seen them, and I was reminded how graphic those stories really were. There is more horrifying stuff in this book, an early version of the hunger games, abuse, murder, poisoning, cannibalism, hanging, but if you got through the previous stories, you'll get through this as well. Lucy Gray begins as an interesting character but then becomes pretty stereotypical, along with many of the other characters. Snow's 'sometimes' friend Sejanus is just so stupid you are relieved he's finally gone.

There's also a really large cast of characters, a catchy beginning but relatively slow-moving story, too many paragraphs of song ballads, and a lightning fast ending that did not make sense, and to-da! Now you know why Snow is such a bad dude!

It was worth reading if you are a Hunger Games fan, but the story is not told evenly and though The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes by Suzanne Collins (2020) (3 stars)

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There’s also a really large cast of characters, a catchy beginning but relatively slow-moving story, too many paragraphs of song ballads, and a lightning fast ending that did not make sense, and to-da! Now you know why Snow is such a bad dude!

It was worth reading if you are a Hunger Games fan, but the story is not told evenly and though “ kaida46’s review. In: LibraryThing, 27.05.2022. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23367868/reviews/207248966> [07.06.2023]

“Prequel. Meet Snow when he is still a teen and learn more about the beginnings of the The Hunger Games. Story and narration are well done.

Ten years after the first rebellion which the rebels lost the capital and the Snow family have fallen on hard times. President’s Snow’s grandson is a mentor. Life is grimmer in the districts, most in the capital are also suffering, but the most sadistic element of the capital is in control and they are playing the Hunger Games, but a much darker version.

This is very dark in many ways, but the author still held me captive. I’m not sure about giving this to all young adults due to how dark it is. Recommended. The end will blow your mind if you have not read reviews before you start!

Borrowed from Lindale Library (Libby) for 14 days.

Amazon description - It is the morning of the reaping that will kick off the 10th annual Hunger Games. In the Capitol, 18-year-old Coriolanus Snow is preparing for his one shot at glory as a mentor in the Games. The once-mighty house of Snow has fallen on hard times, its fate hanging on the slender chance that Coriolanus will be able to out charm, outwit, and outmaneuver his fellow students to mentor the winning tribute.

The odds are against him. He’s been given the humiliating assignment of mentoring the female tribute from District 12, the lowest of the low. Their fates are now completely intertwined - every choice Coriolanus makes could lead to

favor or failure, triumph or ruin. Inside the arena, it will be a fight to the death. Outside the arena, Coriolanus starts to feel for his doomed tribute...and must weigh his need to follow the rules against his desire to survive no matter what it takes.” Gmomaj's review. In: LibraryThing, 27.05.2022. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23367868/reviews/227589385> [07.06.2023]

“I really enjoyed this book. I always wanted to know the backstory of President Snow and now we have one. I was a little surprised by how ‘emotional’ he was, so to speak. I liked how cunning and clever he was, a politician even before he perfect his craft. He had excellent skills and I credit him for what he accomplished, even if some of it was sometimes cruel. He was sly and he was daring and I loved it. I was also surprised by his romance with Lucy Gray. It was at times sting and then at other times weak and uncomfortable sounding. They were definitely never perfect for each other, and I knew that the differences between them would ultimately cause their demise, which it did. But I was surprised by how their falling out changing Coriolanus so much and shaped him into a fearful leader and a cunning tyrant. I thought this was a wonderful edition to this series and I am extremely pleased about how Collins went about crafting this tale.” EvelynNygren's review. In: LibraryThing, 17.11.2022. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23367868/reviews/229618864> [07.06.2023]

“I really wanted to like this. I loved the original books so much - the edge of your seat, emotionally intense, page turning nature of Katniss' journey through Panem was epic. However Snow's is bumbling, inauthentic and poorly executed. He wasn't even fun to hate. There was no motivation to his evil - just stereotypical power hungry, rich ideals. I wasn't moved by his obsession with Lucy, and by the end I was rather disgusted. It's like Collins was trying to make us sympathetic to him and his choices, to "understand" him. I would have had much more understanding had he just been pure evil from the beginning. I don't see how he could have gone from poor, good natured Capitol kid to evil game making genius, it just didn't fit.

The ending was so rushed. I felt like Lucy turned on a dime just to wrap up the book and tie up the loose ends Collins was leaving dangling. She needed to give Coriolanus the motivation and after nearly 500 pages he still didn't have it. Things I did like: getting the origins of some of the songs in the original books. Seeing how the games went from true grit to the enforced spectacle they became. Sejanus! A true rebel - not wanting to be a part of any of it.” muffinbutt1027's review. In: LibraryThing, 17.11.2022. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23367868/reviews/239557457> [07.06.2023]

“OKAY SO This prequel kinda turned into another cursed child for me. You either love it, or your hate it. The first thing I disliked even from picking up the book itself is the fact that it's about Snow. THG trilogy was actually a thought provoking read when I was 11. There's so many characters, and it leaves you thinking for a long time. Out of *all* the characters, Suzanne chose to write about Snow. I would have loved to see a book about Johanna's games, and definitely Finnick's or Haymitch's but *Snow*? Nonetheless I read it. My second complaint is the length. UM ITS 517 PAGES AND MAY I ADD THE WORDS ARE MICROSCOPIC! It took me ages to chore through because for me it was 497 pages of boringness and 20 pages (the last 20 pages of the book) of excitement. It was an origin story, and it did include some interesting things, like the real meaning of The Hanging Tree song and the story of Coriolanus' games. I did enjoy the addition of the songs in the book however the romance was worse than awkward and was just painful. Basically the plot was, snow cheated in the games as a mentor and some singer girl (Lucy Gray Baird) betrays him in the last 20 pages of the book and that ticked me off. The novel could have been condensed down way further than it was. It was packed full of unnecessary info that had no point, and a heck ton of hangings. I would love to see Suzanne make some sort of other series, maybe called Stories from the Tributes that features Haymitch's Games, Johanna's, Finnick's, even Wiress and Beetee would be more interesting than Coriolanus Snow.”ameliaavery's review. In: LibraryThing, 29.12.2022. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23367868/reviews/231939095> [07.06.2023]

“Monsters aren't born - they're made. They are the sum total of all that happened to them. Now we know where President Snow's journey into monsterdom began. We first meet Snow as a more or less typical kid concerned with school, friends, getting into college ... he may not be entirely likable, but he is just a kid. A kid who already has his eye set on becoming President. What happens in the pages of The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes are the first few steps into what created the monster who eventually ruled Panem.” DonnaDeck's review. In: LibraryThing, 16.01.2023. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23367868/reviews/233241123> [07.06.2023]

“Though there is an arena's worth of exploration on the themes of power, privilege, and entitlement, this addition to The Hunger Games series ultimately fails to justify its own existence.” Birdo82's review. In: LibraryThing, 21.01.2023. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23367868/reviews/183789979> [07.06.2023]

“I put off reading this for forever because I wasn't entirely interested, then finally picked it up when I needed an audiobook and I needed it right away, and now I'm surprised to come and see how negative the reviews are! It's been sooo long since I read THE HUNGER GAMES and I knew President Snow was a bad guy, but I couldn't remember his first name so I wasn't sure if Coriolanus was the bad guy or a relative of the bad guy. And as a result I thought his character was so well done! It was lots of fun seeing his emotions towards Lucy Gray and seeing how he thought he felt about people, but then how other desires got in the way. This was a bit long, but with three pretty clear acts, it worked.” whakaora's review. In: LibraryThing, 05.03.2023. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23367868/reviews/236168210> [07.06.2023]

“I really wanted to like this. I loved the original books so much - the edge of your seat, emotionally intense, page turning nature of Katniss' journey through Panem was epic. However Snow's is bumbling, inauthentic and poorly executed. He wasn't even fun to hate. There was no motivation to his evil - just stereotypical power hungry, rich ideals. I wasn't moved by his obsession with Lucy, and by the

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“I put off reading this book b/c I'm not much interested in Coriolanus Snow, but I found the world building very interesting--seeing the early days of the Hunger Games and how different it is. Very interesting read.” MandyPS's review. In: LibraryThing, 13.05.2023. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23367868/reviews/240433182> [07.06.2023]

“A good prequel overall, dragged in places but kept up the signature Hunger Games fast pacing during more engaging bits. The emotions of the story build well and the seeds for the eventual turn in the last chapter are well sown-- even though the change seems to happen in a matter of seconds. The references to the original trilogy of books seem really hammered in and it can be distracting when the narrative is constantly going "See!! Remember that from the original??" In general I would say I had a good time reading this prequel and it gave some cool insights into the past of Panem, but its not as well thought through as the og three.” magykalmira's review. In: LibraryThing, 19.05.2023. Available from: <https://www.librarything.com/work/23367868/reviews/240742303> [07.06.2023]

1.2. Коментари в социални мрежи

Ще бъдат отразени коментари в сайтовете на книжарниците „Хеликон“ (*Helikon*) и „Сиела“ (*Ciela*) и сайтовете за продажба на книги „Озон“ (*ozone.bg*) и *Store.bg*. Коментарите са разделени спрямо изданието, което е коментирано и в хронологичен ред.

Коментари в Helikon:

Няма намерени данни.

Коментари в Ciela:

Няма намерени данни.

Коментари в Ozone:

“Сюзан Колинс никога не може да ме разочарова, имах високи очаквания и книгата ги покри до едно, даже ги надмина! :)” Мария, Ozone, 25.01.2021.
Достъпно на: <https://www.ozone.bg/product/balada-za-poyni-ptitsi-i-zmii/>
[07.06.2023]

“Изчетох я на един дъх, както и останалите от поредицата. Ако сте харесали Игрите на глада, тази книга няма да ви разочарова.” Ана, 12.07.2020.
Достъпно на: <https://www.ozone.bg/product/balada-za-poyni-ptitsi-i-zmii/>
[07.06.2023]

Коментари в Store.bg:

Няма намерени данни.

Изводи от Фаза 1

- Общо 58 проследени и отразени коментара в социалните мрежи
- 31 проследени коментара в социалната мрежа Goodreads
- Общо 25 коментара в социалната мрежа LibraryThing
- 2 проследени коментара в сайта за продажба на книги „Озон“ (*ozone.bg*)

Резултатите от Фаза 1. показват, че за 2020 г. има 22 публикации, за 2021 г. - 12, за 2022 г. - 11 и за 2023 г. - 13.

Дијаграма 1. Коментари в социалните мрежи и онлайн книжарниците в периода 2020 - 2023 г.

Фаза 2. Номинална (формална) обработка

Във втора фаза ще бъде проучено в кои чуждестранни и български дигитални каталози фигурира книгата „The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes”. Ще бъдат изследвани и виртуални книготърговски каталози, в които може да е отразена книгата.

2.1. Дигитални каталози на библиотеки в България

- Няма намерени източници.

2.2. Дигитални каталози на библиотеки в чужбина

Brooklyn Public Library

(<https://www.bklynlibrary.org/item?b=12264335>)

Suzanne Collins. The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes; New York, NY : Scholastic Press, 2020 - 517 pages ; 22 cm.

ISBN [13]: 9781338635171

ISBN [10]: 1338635174

Beverly Hills Public Library

(<https://roxbury.beverlyhills.org/search/Y?SEARCH=The+Ballad+of+Songbird+s+and+Snakes>)

Suzanne Collins. Ballad of song birds and snakes - New York : Scholastic Press, 2020 - 517 pages ; 22 cm.

ISBN [13]: 9781338635171

ISBN [10]: 1338635174

New York Public Library

(<https://nypl.na2.iivega.com/search/card?id=e61f6f98-d9a7-59fd-af73-400e650ca81c&entityType=FormatGroup>)

Suzanne Collins. The Ballad of song birds and snakes - New York : Scholastic Press, 2020 - 517 pages ; 22 cm.

ISBN [13]: 9781338635171

ISBN [10]: 1338635174

2.3. Български дигитални книготърговски каталози

Книгомания

(<https://knigomania.bg/the-ballad-of-songbirds-and-snakes-a-hunger-games-novel.html>)

Suzanne Collins. The Ballad of song birds and snakes. - SCHOLASTIC 2020. - 528 с.

Ozone.bg

(<https://www.ozone.bg/product/balada-za-poyni-ptitsi-i-zmii/>)

Suzanne Collins. The Ballad of song birds and snakes. - Екслибрис 2020. - 528 с.

Изводи от Фаза 2

Книгата „The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes“ от Сюзан Колинс е отразена в общо 5 пъти: 5 в библиотеки - 0 български и в 3 чуждестранни, и в 2 български дигитални книготърговски каталога.

Поради липсата на информация данните не могат да се проследят по години, затова ще бъдат визуализирани според видовете каталози, в който е отразена книгата.

Диаграма 2. Отразяване на книгата в дигитални каталози, според вида каталог, в периода 2020 - 2023 г.

Фаза 3. Редукция (аналитико-синтетична) обработка на съдържанието

Във Фаза 3 ще бъдат търсени анотациите, анонсите, резюметата и съкратените версии на книгата „The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes” на Сюзан Колинс, както и новините и съобщенията за нея.

3.1. Анотации, анонси, резюмета и съкратени версии на книгата

Анотация на книгата е написана от издателството и мултиплицирана и превеждана многократно в онлайн медии и книжарници.

*Ambition will fuel him.
Competition will drive him.
But power has its price.*

It is the morning of the reaping that will kick off the tenth annual Hunger Games. In the Capitol, eighteen-year-old Coriolanus Snow is preparing for his one shot at glory as a mentor in the Games. The once-mighty house of Snow has fallen on hard times, its fate hanging on the slender chance that Coriolanus will be able to outcharm, outwit, and outmaneuver his fellow students to mentor the winning tribute.

The odds are against him. He's been given the humiliating assignment of mentoring the female tribute from District 12, the lowest of the low. Their fates are now completely intertwined - every choice Coriolanus makes could lead to favor or failure, triumph or ruin. Inside the arena, it will be a fight to the death. Outside the arena, Coriolanus starts to feel for his doomed tribute and must weigh his need to follow the rules against his desire to survive no matter what it takes.

The Hunger Games Notes. In: WordPress, [2020]. Available from: <https://hungergamesnotes.wordpress.com/15-the-ballad-of-songbirds-and-snakes> [08.06.2023]

Амбицията го подхранва. Състезанието го движи. Но властта има висока цена.

Сутринта на Жътвата, с която започват десетите Игри на глада. В Капитола осемнадесетгодишния Кориолан Сноу се подготвя за този единствен шанс да спечели слава като ментор в Игрите. За някога могъщата фамилия Сноу са настъпили трудни времена и съдбата ѝ зависи от нищожния шанс Кориолан да успее да бъде по-чаровен, по-умен и по-изобретателен от съучениците си, за да стане ментор на трибута победител.

Вероятността да спечели е малка. Пада му се унижителната задача да бъде ментор на момичето трибут от Окръг 12, най-незначителния от всички. Съдбите на двамата сега са напълно преплетени - всяко решение на Кориолан може да доведе до победа или провал, триумф или поражение. На арената битката ще бъде на живот и на смърт. Извън арената Кориолан започва да съчувства на обречения си трибут... и трябва да балансира между потребността си да следва правилата и желанието да оцелее на всяка цена.

Превод на анотацията - Ex Libris, 2023. Available from: <https://exlibris.bg/produkt> [08.06.2023]

Написани са и резюмета за книгата, заради големия интерес на читателите.

The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes/Summary. In: The Hunger games Wiki, 31.05.2020. Available from: https://thehungergames.fandom.com/wiki/The_Ballad_of_Songbirds_and_Snakes/Summary [08.06.2023]

Vento, Michael. The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes Summary and Analysis. In: Current Wave, 23.07.2020. Available from: <https://currentwave.org/the-ballad-of-songbirds-and-snakes-review-and-analysis> [08.06.2023]

Brock, Zoë. The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes Plot Summary. In: LitCharts, 16.08.2021. Available from: <https://www.litcharts.com/lit/the-ballad-of-songbirds-and-snakes/summary> [08.06.2023]

Kennedy, Patrick. Suduiko, Aaron. The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes Summary. In: GradeSaver, 22.03.2022. Available from: <https://www.gradesaver.com/the-ballad-of-songbirds-and-snakes/study-guide/summary> [08.06.2023]

3.2. Новини и съобщения за книгата

A ‘Hunger Games’ Prequel Focuses on an Unlikely Character. In: New York Times, 19.06.2020. Available from: <https://www.nytimes.com/2020/05/19/books/review/hunger-games-prequel-ballad-of-songbirds-and-snakes.html> [08.06.2023]

5 things to know about 'Hunger Games' prequel book 'Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes'. In: USA Today, 2020. Available from: <https://eu.usatoday.com/story/entertainment/books/2020/05/19/hunger-games-ballad-of-songbirds-snakes-what-to-know/5218784002> [08.06.2023]

Film adaptation of new Hunger Games book, The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes, already in works. In: CBC, 21.04.2020. Available from: <https://www.cbc.ca/books/film-adaptation-of-new-hunger-games-book-the-ballad-of-songbirds-and-snakes-already-in-works-1.5539944> [08.06.2023]

‘Hunger Games’ Prequel ‘The Ballad of Songbirds And Snakes’ Moves Forward At Lionsgate With Series Director Francis Lawrence. In: Deadline, 21.04.2020. Available from: <https://deadline.com/2020/04/hunger-games-prequel-ballad-of-songbirds-and-snakes-francis-lawrence-to-direct-1202913869> [08.06.2023]

In ‘The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes,’ Suzanne Collins reveals the origin of the Hunger Games. In: The Washington Post, 26.05.2020. Available from: https://www.washingtonpost.com/entertainment/books/in-the-ballad-of-songbirds-and-snakes-suzanne-collins-reveals-the-origin-of-the-hunger-games/2020/05/26/08c61f4c-9f85-11ea-9590-1858a893bd59_story.html [08.06.2023]

Suzanne Collins Revisited ‘The Hunger Games’ to “Plant the Seeds” on Snow’s Backstory. In: The Hollywood reporter, 19.05.2020. Available from: <https://www.hollywoodreporter.com/news/general-news/suzanne-collins-talks-hunger-games-prequel-ballad-songbirds-snakes-1295145> [08.06.2023]

SCHOLASTIC ANNOUNCES SANTINO FONTANA AS NARRATOR FOR AUDIO EDITION OF THE BALLAD OF SONGBIRDS AND SNAKES BY SUZANNE COLLINS. In: Scholastic, 08.04.2020. Available from: <http://mediaroom.scholastic.com/press->

[release/scholastic-announces-santino-fontana-narrator-audio-edition-ballad-songbirds-and-snake](#) [08.06.2023]

Will There Be Another Hunger Games Book? 2021 Updates and Everything We Know So Far. In: Epic Stream, 15.12.2021. Available from: <https://epicstream.com/article/will-there-be-another-hunger-games-book-2021-updates-and-everything-we-know-so-far-book-2021-updates-and-everything-we-know-so-far> [08.06.2023]

The Hunger Games Prequel, Songbirds, Is a Satire on the Ruling Class. In: Jacobin, 06.11.2021. Available from: <https://jacobin.com/2021/06/hunger-games-prequel-ballad-of-songbirds-and-snakes-suzanne-collins-review> [08.06.2023]

The Hunger Games Prequel: What to Know About The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes. In: CBR, 11.08.2021. Available from: <https://www.cbr.com/hunger-games-prequel-film-guide> [08.06.2023]

‘Hunger Games’ Prequel To Start Production In First Half Of 2022, Lionsgate Film Boss Joe Drake Says. In: Dead Line, 05.08.2021. Available from: <https://deadline.com/2021/08/hunger-games-prequel-ballad-songbirds-snakes-movie-production-start-in-first-half-of-2022-1234810116> [08.06.2023]

Everything we know so far about the explosive new ‘Hunger Games’ prequel. In: Vogue, 21.09.2022. Available from: <https://vogue.sg/hunger-games-prequel-ballad-of-songbirds-and-snakes> [08.06.2023]

Rachel Zegler Reveals Behind-the-Scenes Look at ‘The Hunger Games’ Prequel ‘The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes’. In: Variety, 20.10.2022. Available from: <https://variety.com/2022/film/news/rachel-zegler-behind-the-scenes-hunger-games-prequel-ballad-songbirds-snakes-1235410465> [08.06.2023]

Why ‘Hunger Games: The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes’ Will Be a Standalone Film. In: Collider, 15.11.2022. Available from: <https://collider.com/hunger-games-ballad-of-songbirds-and-snakes-standalone-movie-francis-lawrence-comments> [08.06.2023]

‘Hunger Games’ Prequel ‘The Ballad Of Songbirds And Snakes’ Gets 2023 Release Date - CinemaCon. In: Dead Line, 28.04.2022. Available from: <https://deadline.com/2022/04/hunger-games-prequel-the-ballad-of-songbirds-and-snakes-theatrical-release-1235012382> [08.06.2023]

All the Details on ‘Hunger Games’ Prequel ‘The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes’. In: IndieWire, 21.10.2022. Available from: <https://www.indiewire.com/feature/hunger-games-ballad-of-songbirds-and-snakes-release-date-cast-1234735970> [08.06.2023]

“Балада за пойни птици и змии”, Хънтър Шафър, Рейчъл Зиглър и още новини от предисторията на “Игрите на глада”. В: LifeStyle, 07.07.2022. Available from: <https://lifestyle.bg/stories/balada-za-poyni-ptitsi-i-zmii-hantar->

shafar-reychal-zeglar-i-oshte-novini-ot-predistoriyata-na-igrите-na-glada.html
[08.06.2023]

“Балада за пойни птици и змии” ще получи своята екранизация. В: WebCafe, 29.04.2022. Available from: <https://webcafe.bg/kino/balada-za-poyni-ptitsi-i-zmii-shte-poluchi-svoyata-ekranizatsiya.html> [08.06.2023]

Everything to Know About The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes. In: Bazaar, 28.04.2023. Available from: <https://www.harpersbazaar.com/culture/film-tv/a43741482/the-ballad-of-songbirds-and-snakes-release-date-cast-news-spoilers> [08.06.2023]

‘The Hunger Games: The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes’ Prequel Book Explained. In: Collider, 28.04.2023. Available from: <https://collider.com/hunger-games-ballad-songbirds-snakes-prequel-book-explained> [08.06.2023]

‘The Hunger Games: The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes’ Gets Full Trailer at CinemaCon. In: The Hollywood reporter, 27.04.2023. Available from: <https://www.hollywoodreporter.com/movies/movie-news/hunger-games-ballad-of-songbirds-and-snakes-full-trailer-1235199988> [08.06.2023]

‘Hunger Games’ Prequel ‘The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes’ Debuts Grim, Sweeping First Trailer at CinemaCon. In: Variety, 27.04.2023. Available from: <https://variety.com/2023/film/news/hunger-games-prequel-ballad-of-songbirds-snakes-trailer-cinemacon-1235587096> [08.06.2023]

The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes: Hunger Games prequel release date, cast, plot, trailer and everything you need to know. In: Digital Spy, 29.03.2023. Available from: <https://www.digitalspy.com/movies/a43426782/ballad-songbirds-snakes-hunger-games-release-date> [08.06.2023]

Everything We Know About the Hunger Games Prequel Film, The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes. In: Seventeen, 28.04.2023. Available from: <https://www.seventeen.com/celebrity/movies-tv/a39862098/hunger-games-film-ballad-of-songbirds-and-snakes> [08.06.2023]

Ballad Of Songbirds And Snakes - Cast, Trailer, Story & Everything We Know. In: Screen Rant, 29.04.2023. Available from: <https://screenrant.com/hunger-games-prequel-movie-release-date-story> [08.06.2023]

The Hunger Games: The Ballad of Songbirds & Snakes: Release date, trailer, cast, story, and how to catch up. In: Pocket lint, 30.04.2023. Available in: <https://www.pocket-lint.com/hunger-games-prequel-movie-ballad-of-songbirds-and-snakes-release-date> [08.06.2023]

Книгата „The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes“ е била аотирана и представяна в съкратен вид пъти 6 пъти - 5 пъти на английски и 1 на български. Онлайн са публикувани 26 новини и съобщения, които са свързани предимно с екранизирането на книгата.

Резултатите от Фаза 3

Редукция (аналитико-синтетична обработка) на съдържанието показват, че за периода 2020-2023 г. книгата “The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes“ на Сюзан Колинс е обект на Редукция (аналитико-синтетична обработка) на съдържанието общо 26 пъти. През 2020 г. книгата е отразена в 7 публикации, през 2021 г. в 4, през 2022 г. в 7, през 2023 г. в 8.

Резултатите от Фаза 3. Редукция (формите на аналитико-синтетична обработка) на съдържанието на книгата доказват, че книгата „The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes“ е получила сериозен информационен резонанс сред качествените читатели и се е осъществила като медия.

Диаграма 3. Редукция (аналитико-синтетична обработка) на съдържанието в периода 2020 - 2023 г.

Фаза 4. Репродукция (деривация) на книгата

Във Фаза 4 ще бъдат търсени преводи, различни формати на книгата и цитирания на книгата „The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes“ от Сюзан Колинс.

Преводи

Книгата „The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes“ на Сюзан Колинс е преведена на повече от 20 езика, сред които български, френски, испански и немски.

- **Български:** Колинс, Сюзан. Балада за пойни птици и змии. - София: Ексилибрис, 2020. - 496 с.
- **Френски:** Collins, Suzanne. La ballade du serpent et de l’oiseau chanteur. - Paris: Pocket Jeunesse, 2020. - 560 p.
- **Испански:** Collins, Suzanne. Balada de Pajaros Cantores y Serpientes. - Barcelona: RBA Molino, 2020.
- **Немски:** Collins, Suzanne. Die Tribute von Panem: das Lied von Vogel und Schlange. - Hamburg: Verlag Friedrich Oetinger, 2020.

Цитирания

Цитати или откъси от книгата „The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes“ на Сюзан Колинс са поместени в следните онлайн източници:

Book Review: The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes by Suzanne Collins. - In: Medium, 10.08.2020. Available from: [Book Review: The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes by Suzanne Collins | by Grace Regan | Medium](#) [08.06.2023]

Review: The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes. - In: The Sassy Library Fox, 11.11.2020. Available from: <https://thesassylibraryfox.wordpress.com/2020/11/11/review-the-ballad-of-songbirds-and-snakes-suzanne-collins> [08.06.2023]

Book Review: The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes by Suzanne Collins (The Hunger Games #0). - In: The Bookish Elf, [2023]. Available from: <https://www.bookishelf.com/book-review-the-ballad-of-songbirds-and-snakes-by-suzanne-collins-the-hunger-games-0> [08.06.2023]

Изводи от Фаза 4

Книгата „The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes“ е преведена на множество езици, което я прави достъпна за широк кръг от читатели по целия свят.

Търсенето в Google предоставя около 230 000 резултата, които са свързани с книгата „The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes“ на Сюзан Колинс. Резултатите дават информация за ревюта, резюмета и анотации на книгата, не толкова за нейното цитиране или цитирани извадки от нея. В по-голямата си част резултатите насочват потребителя към онлайн книжарници, откъдето книгата може да бъде закупена.

Резултатите от Фаза 4. Репродукция (деривация) на книгата доказват, че книгата „The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes“ се е осъществила като медия,

защото част от намерените резултати показват, че цитати от книгата са заимствани 2 (два) пъти през 2020 г. и 1 (един) път през 2023 г.

Диаграма 4. Изводи от репродукция (деривация) на книгата за периода 2020 - 2023 г.

Фаза 5. Текуща (оперативна) критика

Във Фаза 5 ще бъдат търсени отзиви и рецензии в медиите, публикувани ревьюта (читателски прегледи) и интервюта относно книгата „The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes“ от Сюзан Колинс.

5.1. Отзиви и рецензии в медиите

Womack, Philip. The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes - a sleek Hunger Games prequel. - In: The Guardian, 19.05.2020. Available from: [The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes review - a sleek Hunger Games prequel | Suzanne Collins | The Guardian](#) [08.06.2023]

Grady, Constance. The new Hunger Games prequel is introspective and dark as hell. - In: Vox, 19.05.2020. Available from: [Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes review: An eerie Hunger Games prequel - Vox](#) [08.06.2023]

Quinn, Annalisa. The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes Is A Lackluster Prequel to The Hunger Games. - In: NPR, 19.05.2020. Available from: ['The Hunger Games' Prequel 'The Ballad Of Songbirds And Snakes' Is Lackluster : NPR](#) [08.06.2023]

Franich, Darren. The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes review: hunger Games prequel’s darkly funny, way too long. - In: Entertainment Weekly, 19.05.2020. Available from: <https://ew.com/books/book-reviews/ballad-songbirds-snakes-review-hunger-games> [08.06.2023]

Lyall, Sarah. A Hunger Games Prequel Focuses on an Unlikely Character. - In: The New York Times, 19.05.2020. Available from: [A ‘Hunger Games’ Prequel Focuses on an Unlikely Character - The New York Times \(nytimes.com\)](#) [08.06.2023]

McCluskey, Megan. The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes Adds New Dimensions to the One-Note Villainy of the Hunger Games’ President Snow. - In: Times, 19.05.2020. Available from: <https://time.com/5838257/the-ballad-of-songbirds-and-snakes-review> [08.06.2023]

O’Connell, Alex. The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes by Suzanne Collins review - the Hunger Games are back. - In: The UK Times, 19.05.2020. Available from: [The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes by Suzanne Collins review – the Hunger Games are back \(thetimes.co.uk\)](#) [08.06.2023]

Cox Gurdon, Meghan. Children’s Books: Feeding the Hunger for a Prequel. - In: The Wall Street Journal, 19.05.2020. Available from: [Children’s Books: Feeding the Hunger for a Prequel - WSJ](#) [08.06.2023]

Corbett, Sue. The Hunger Games’ Suzanne Collins Writes Prequel, The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes: PEOPLE Review. - In: People Magazine, 19.05.2020. Available from: <https://people.com/movies/the-hunger-games-suzanne-collins-writes-prequel-the-ballad-of-songbirds-and-snakes-read-peoples-review> [08.06.2023]

Radulovic, Petrana. The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes is a darkly satisfying origin story. - In: Polygon, 20.05.2020. Available from: [Hunger Games prequel review: The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes is darkly satisfying - Polygon](#) [08.06.2023]

Miller, Laura. The New Hunger Games Novel Abandons Adolescent Fantasy for Big Ideas. - In: Slate, 21.05.2020. Available from: [The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes review: Hunger Games prequel novel abandons adolescent fantasy for big ideas. \(slate.com\)](#) [08.06.2023]

Jones, Nicolette. Children’s book of the week: The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes by Suzanne Collins. - In: The Sunday Times UK, 24.05.2020. Available from: [Children’s book of the week: The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes by Suzanne Collins \(thetimes.co.uk\)](#) [08.06.2023]

Tanabe, Karin. The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes, Suzanne Collins reveals the origin of the Hunger Games. - In: The Washington Post, 26.05.2020. Available from: [‘The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes’ by Suzanne Collins book review - The Washington Post](#) [08.06.2023]

Murad, Mahvesh. Unfavourable Odds: The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes by Suzanne Collins. - In: Tor, 10.06.2020. Available from: <https://www.tor.com/2020/06/10/book-reviews-the-ballad-of-songbirds-and-snakes-by-suzanne-collins> [08.06.2023]

Dalezioiu, Madalena. Review: The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes by Suzanne Collins. - In: The Nerd Daily, 22.07.2020. Available from: <https://thenerdaily.com/the-ballad-of-songbirds-and-snakes-by-suzanne-collins> [08.06.2023]

Mondor, Colleen. Colleen Mondor Reviews The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes by Suzanne Collins. - In: Locus, 13.08.2020. Available from: <https://locusmag.com/2020/08/colleen-mondor-reviews-the-ballad-of-songbirds-and-snakes-by-suzanne-collins> [08.06.2023]

5.2. Публикувани ревята (читателски прегледи)

Walton, David. The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes (A Hunger Games Novel). - In: New York Journal of Books, 19.05.2020. Available from: [a book review by David Walton: The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes \(A Hunger Games Novel\) \(nyjournalofbooks.com\)](http://nyjournalofbooks.com/a-book-review-by-david-walton-the-ballad-of-songbirds-and-snakes-a-hunger-games-novel) [08.06.2023]

All Of My Thoughts Reading “The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes” by Suzanne Collins (Contains Spoilers). - In: Peace.Love.Veggies, 11.06.2020. Available from: <https://peaceandloveandveggies.com/2020/06/11/all-of-my-thoughts-reading-the-ballad-of-songbirds-and-snakes-by-suzanne-collins-contains-spoilers> [08.06.2023]

Book Review: The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes by Suzanne Collins. - In: Medium, 10.08.2020. Available from: [Book Review: The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes by Suzanne Collins | by Grace Regan | Medium](https://medium.com/@graceregans/book-review-the-ballad-of-songbirds-and-snakes-by-suzanne-collins-by-grace-regan) [08.06.2023]

Review: The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes. - In: The Sassy Library Fox, 11.11.2020. Available from: <https://thesassylibraryfox.wordpress.com/2020/11/11/review-the-ballad-of-songbirds-and-snakes-suzanne-collins> [08.06.2023]

Dischler, Heidi. Book Review: The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes by Suzanne Collins. - In: Heidi Dischler, 25.03.2021. Available from: <https://www.heididischler.com/book-review-the-ballad-of-songbirds-and-snakes-by-suzanne-collins> [08.06.2023]

Brown, Reagan. Review: The ballad of Songbirds and Snakes by Suzanne Collins. - In: The Fanfare, 13.05.2021. Available from: <https://bpsfanfare.com/11350/uncategorized/review-the-ballad-of-songbirds-and-snakes-by-suzanne-collins> [08.06.2023]

Book Review - The ballad of Songbirds and Snakes. - In: Sci- fi Fantasy Lit Chick, 01.11.2022. Available from: <https://scififantasylitchick.wordpress.com/2022/11/01/book-review-the-ballad-of-songbirds-and-snakes> [08.06.2023]

Book Review: The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes by Suzanne Collins (The Hunger Games #0). - In: The Bookish Elf, [2023]. Available from:

<https://www.bookishelf.com/book-review-the-ballad-of-songbirds-and-snakes-by-suzanne-collins-the-hunger-games-0> [08.06.2023]

The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes by Suzanne Collins - book review. - In: WordPress, [2023]. Available from: <https://wishfullyreading.wordpress.com/2020/07/14/the-ballad-of-songbirds-and-snakes-by-suzanne-collins-book-review> [08.06.2023]

5.3. Интервюта за книгата

Levithan, David. Suzanne Collins on The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes. - In: On Our Minds, 19.05.2020. Available from: [Suzanne Collins on The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes | On Our Minds \(oomscholasticblog.com\)](https://www.oomscholasticblog.com/suzanne-collins-on-the-ballad-of-songbirds-and-snakes) [08.06.2023]

Perez, Lexy. Suzanne Collins revisited The Hunger Games to “Plant the Seeds” on Snow’s Backstory. - In: The Hollywood Reporter, 19.05.2020. Available from: <https://www.hollywoodreporter.com/news/general-news/suzanne-collins-talks-hunger-games-prequel-ballad-songbirds-snakes-1295145> [08.06.2023]

Изводи от Фаза 5

Книгата има голям брой рецензии и оценъчни статии, отразени в медиите. намерени резултати има и за публикувани ревюта от читатели под формата на блогове. Общественият отзвук е значителен и интересът към книгата е голям. Това доказва, че „The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes” се е осъществила като медия.

Резултатите от Фаза 5

За периода 2020 - 2023 г. книгата „The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes” е отразена в:

- 16 отзива и рецензии, публикувани в медиите през 2020 г.
- 9 публикувани читателски ревюта, 4 от които са публикувани през 2020 г., 2 - през 2021 г., 1 - през 2022 г. и 2 - през 2023 г.
- 2 интервюта с авторката от 2020 г.

Диаграма 5. Редукция (аналитико-синтетична обработка) на съдържанието в периода 2020 - 2023 г.

Фаза 6. Експертна (научна) критика

6.1. Професионални награди

Няма открити резултати за награди на книгата „The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes” от Сюзан Колинс.

6.2. Изследвания и интерпретации

Изследванията и интерпретациите на книгата „The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes“ от Сюзан Колинс включват резюмета, анализи и изследвания, както и интерпретации по формата на статии. Всички тези източници са показани във Фаза 3 и Фаза 5.

Изводи от Фаза 6

Експертната (научна) критика, предоставена в тази фаза доказва, че книгата „The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes“ от Сюзан Колинс се е осъществила като медия, поради това, че е обект на голям брой публикации от различно естество заради интереса и противоречието, които предизвиква у читатели и експерти.

Фаза 7. Медиаморфози

Във Фаза 7 ще бъдат търсени медиаморфози на книгата „The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes“ от Сюзан Колинс в периода 2020 - 2023 г.

7.1. Екранизация

Книгата на Сюзан Колинс „The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes“ предстои да бъде екранизирана на 17.11.2023 г.

7.2. Дискусии за книгата

На 29 май 2020 г. се е провела виртуална дискусия, относно книгата, с участието на автора Сюзан Колинс и редакторът на книгата Дейвид Левитан. Книгата е избрана за дискусия в специалната селекция на “Barnes & Noble YA Book Club”.

Изводи от Фаза 7

По книгата „The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes“ предстои да бъде направена екранизация през 2023 г. и е направена една виртуална дискусия в “Barnes & Noble YA Book Club”. В: TinyBeans, 27.04.2020. Available from: <https://tinybeans.com/barnes-noble-the-ballad-of-songbirds-and-snakes-hunger-games-virtual-event> [06.06.2023]

Резултатите от Фаза 7

Предвидената екранизация не може да бъде включена в окончателните резултати, но книгата се осъществява като медия, поради интерес от актьори и режисьори, както и поради проведена дискусия. Резултатът е само **един** и от една година, затова няма нужда от диаграма.

Фаза 8. Историзация

Във фаза 8 ще бъдат търсени класации, в които е включена книгата „The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes” на Сюзан Колинс в периода 2020-2023 г.

8.1. Класации на книгата

Първо място в седмичната класация на “USA Today Best-Selling Books” през първите две седмици след издаването на книгата. В: USA Today, 2023. Available from: <https://eu.usatoday.com/story/entertainment/books/2020/06/09/hunger-games-primer-things-remember-ballad-songbirds-and-snakes> [06.06.2023]

Първо място за най-продаваната книга през първата половина на 2020 г. в Wall Street Journal. В: Scholastic, 2023. Available from: <http://mediaroom.scholastic.com/press-release/scholastic-publish-paperback-editions-hunger-games-prequel-ballad-songbirds-and-snakes> [06.06.2023]

Първо място за най-продаваната книга през първата половина на 2020 г. в Publisher Weekly bestsellers list. В: Scholastic, 2023. Available from: <http://mediaroom.scholastic.com/press-release/scholastic-publish-paperback-editions-hunger-games-prequel-ballad-songbirds-and-snakes> [06.06.2023]

Второ място в годишната класацията “Goodreads Choice Awards 2020” в категорията “Best young adult fantasy and science fiction”. В: Goodreads, 08.12.2020 г. Available from: <https://www.goodreads.com/choiceawards/best-young-adult-fantasy-books-2020> [06.06.2023]

Изводи от Фаза 8

Книгата „The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes” е включена в 4 класации през 2020 г. и заема първите позиции. През годините 2021-2023 г. не е включвана в класации.

Резултатите от Фаза 8

Историзацията доказва, че книгата „The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes“ на Сюзан Колинс се е осъществила като медия. Резултатите са само от 2020 г., затова няма нужда от диаграма.

Изводи и обобщение

Рекапитулация на резултатите

Общият брой на всички открити резултати от информационния мониторинг във всяка от осемте фази на информационен резонанс на книгата „The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes“ на Сюзан Колинс е визуализиран в Диаграма 6.

Диаграма 6. Информационен резонанс на книгата „Балада за пойни птици и змии“ по фази за периода 2020 - 2023 г.

Най-много форми на обратна връзка се наблюдават във Фаза 1. Симултанни онлайн практики и пряка обратна връзка - общо 58 резултата.

Фаза 2. Номинална (формална) обработка показва, че книгата е отразена 5 пъти с метаданни в дигитални каталози на библиотеки и онлайн книготърговски каталози.

Във Фаза 3. Редукция (аналитико-синтетична обработка) на съдържанието информационния резонанс под формата на анотации и новини за книгата е осъществена 26 пъти.

Фаза 4. Репродукция (деривация) на книгата отразява 2 резултата - книгата.

Във Фаза 5. Текуща (оперативна) критика има общо 27 резултата - 16 отзива и рецензии, 9 публикувани читателски ревюта, 2 интервюта с авторката.

Във Фаза 6. Експертна (научна) критика, професионални награди; изследвания и интерпретации за информационен резонанс на книгата - изследванията и интерпретациите на книгата „The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes“ от Сюзан Колинс включват резюмета, анализи и изследвания, както и интерпретации по формата на статии. Всички тези източници са показани във Фаза 3 и Фаза 5.

Във Фаза 7. Медиаморфози са отрити 1 резултата. По книгата е проведена 1 виртуална дискусия.

Фаза 8. Историзация отразява 4 резултата - участието на книгата в годишни класации.

В Диаграма 7 са визуализирани резултатите от осемте фази за информационен резонанс на книгата „Балада за пойни птици и змии“ на Сюзан Колинс, разделени по години.

Диаграма 7. Информационен резонанс на книгата „Балада за пойни птици и змии“ по години за периода 2020 - 2023 г.

Изданието е реализирано най-добре през 2020 г. - годината на издаване, когато резултатите са общо 57. На второ място е 2023 г. с 24 резултата, следвана от 2022 г. с 19 и 2021 г. с 18 резултата.

Финален извод

Резултатите от проведеното проучване за периода 2020 - 2023 г. доказват успешното комуникиране на книгата „The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes“ на Сюзан Колинс и осъществяването ѝ като медия. Създадена е ефективна комуникация между автора и читателите и е провокирана бърза и мащабна обратна връзка.

Книгата успява да се реализира във всички фази за периода 2020 - 2023 г. Най-голям успех има във фаза 1 „Симултанни и интерактивни онлайн практики“, където общия брой на резултатите е 58. Книгата е отразена 5 пъти с метаданни в дигитални каталози на библиотеки и онлайн книготърговски каталози и е обект на Редукция (аналитико-синтетична обработка) на съдържанието 26 пъти. Във фаза 5 „Текуща (оперативна) критика“ са регистрирани общо 27 резултата. Проведена е виртуална дискусия за книгата (покриване на резонанса във фаза 7). Книгата присъства и в 4 годишни класации

за книги, които предполагат нейната бъдеща историзация (покрытие на резонанса във фаза 8).

Читателите получават най-лесен достъп до метаданните на книгата чрез различните виртуални каталози.

Книгата получава най-голям информационен резонанс във Фаза 1 „Симултани и интерактивни онлайн практики и пряка обратна връзка”, което доказва значението на социалните мрежи и заинтересоваността на автора не само от продажбите на книгата му, а и от читателите. Също така по този начин хората, които не са прочели книгата, могат да прочетат коментарите и резюметата, които да им помогнат да разберат дали искат да я прочетат.

Книгата успява да се докаже във всички фази от изследването, което я прави осъществила се като медия.